

MAGNETIC STUDY OF PHOTOTROPIC COMPOUNDS. MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITIES OF *p*-DIMETHYLAMINO- AND *p*-DIETHYLAMINO-PHENYLIMINOCAMPHORS.

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Changes in the values of magnetic susceptibilities of *p*-dimethylamino- and *p*-diethylamino-phenyliminocamphors with exposure to light have been studied. Attempts have been made to explain the results obtained in the light of the formation of free radicals.

Bhatnagar, Kapur and Hashmi (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 15, 512) measured the magnetic susceptibility of a large number of phototropic compounds and did not find any change in the magnetic susceptibility value of these substances on exposure to light. This shows that all of them are perhaps identical in constitution and the difference in colour may be due to their states of aggregation being different.

The view that phototropic change involves a polymerisation or depolymerisation (Padoa, *Atti Acad. Lincei*, 1913, 22, 1500) also is not supported by these observations. Had there been any polymerisation, it would have been accompanied by a change in the magnetic susceptibility on exposure to light.

The present investigation deals with the magnetic susceptibilities of *p*-dimethylamino- and *p*-diethylamino-phenyliminocamphors (Singh and Singh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 219, 768) both of which are phototropic.

EXPERIMENTAL.

p-Dimethylaminophenyliminocamphor, prepared by the method of Singh and Singh (*loc. cit.*) gives a poor yield with a lot of tarry products which render the separation and purification very difficult. The method was, therefore, modified as follows.

p-Dimethylaminoaniline hydrochloride (25% more than the molecular quantity) was treated with a solution of caustic potash. The free base liberated was extracted with ether and the ethereal solution was repeatedly washed with water. It was then dried over anhydrous calcium chloride and evaporated to a small bulk (5 c. c.). Molecular quantity of camphorquinon and a little anhydrous sodium sulphate were added and the mixture was heated for three hours on the water-bath. After cooling, water was added to precipitate the compound. It was recrystallised from 60% alcohol as a light brown fluffy crystalline mass, m.p. 135.5° after deepening in colour.

p-Diethylaminophenyliminocamphor was prepared by a method exactly similar to the one described above. It was crystallised from dilute alcohol into light orange needles melting at 102.5° to a deep red coloured liquid.

p-Dimethylamino compound is yellow and becomes deep yellow with an orange tinge on exposure to light. *p*-Diethylamino compound is, however, light orange, becoming scarlet on exposure.

p-Dimethylamino Compound.

This compound shows diamagnetism but the value is found to increase gradually till it becomes paramagnetic, if the substance is not protected from light as the following figures indicate.

Obs.	1	2	3
$\chi \times 10^6$	-0.883	-0.322	+0.980

If, however, the substance were kept in the dark, the observed value even after three days was found to be -0.881×10^{-6} i.e. it did not change at all.

It is, however, evident that exposure to light profoundly affected the χ -value of this compound. The influence of exposure to light for different intervals of time was, therefore, studied and the results obtained for two different samples under experimental conditions are represented in Table I.

TABLE I.

Time of exposure.	Magnetic susceptibility $\times 10^6$			Sample in C_6H_6 -soln.
	Sample in bulk No. 1.	No. 2.	Sample in tube.	
0 min	-0.883	-0.881	-0.8808	-0.8806
5	+0.911	-0.199	-0.8174	+1.057
10	+1.072	+1.068	-0.8032	+1.082
15	+1.077	+1.088	-0.7880	+1.085
20	+1.074	+1.080	-0.7725	+1.085
30	—	+1.091	-0.7423	—
40	—	—	-0.7430	—
45	—	+1.085	—	—
50	—	—	-0.7427	—
60	—	+1.087	-0.7432	—
80	—	—	-0.7432	—

Columns 2 and 3 of Table I represent results for two different samples exposed to light in bulk under identical condition. Column 4 embodies the values when the sample was exposed to sunlight in a tube. In this case the value falls from -0.8808 to -0.7423 after 30 minutes, after which further exposure has no effect. This probably suggests that only the surface layer is affected by light.

With a view to throwing, if possible, further light on the mechanism of this process, magnetic study of the substance in benzene solution was also made (result in column 5, Table I). This substance was dissolved in benzene (A. R. quality) to have 1% solution. The susceptibility value of benzene was previously determined to be -0.7108×10^{-6} . The same values for the solution after exposure to light for different intervals of time were determined, from which the values for the solid solute were deduced according to the formula,

$$\chi_{\text{solid}} = \frac{\chi_{\text{soln}} - \left(1 - \frac{P}{100}\right) \chi_{\text{solvent}}}{P/100}$$

where P represents the weight of the solid compound in 100 g. of the solution. It may be mentioned here that in all the above cases, if the sample be not exposed to light but preserved in the dark, the χ -values obtained do not materially differ from the original value, the values being -0.8774×10^{-6} and -0.8801×10^{-6} for columns 4 and 5 respectively (Table I).

p-Diethylamino Compound.

A similar study was made in the case of *p*-diethyl compound. Table II records the values of magnetic susceptibility when the compound was exposed to light in bulk for different intervals of time and the changes in colour also noted.

TABLE II.

Time of exposure.	$\chi \times 10^6$.	Colour.
0 min.	-0.6988	Deep yellow
5	-0.3336	Brownish red
15	-0.3087	"
30	-0.2406	Deep brown
45	-0.2088	Deep brownish red
60	-0.2085	"
75	-0.2080	"

It was noted that the compound, when exposed to light, assumed a scarlet colour, but as soon as it was removed from light, the scarlet colour began to fade. After about twelve hours it regained its original yellow colour.

Hence to determine the χ -value of the compound, when it had the scarlet-red colour, the surface of the compound was exposed to reflected light, while the specimen tube was at the balance and the reading was taken when scarlet-red colour was assumed by the compound.

Table III shows the effect of light on the surface of the compound (when the colour was scarlet).

TABLE III.

Time of exposure.	$\chi \times 10^6$.	Colour.
0 min.	-0.6988	Yellow
5	+1.738	Scarlet
10	+1.7298	"

Singh and Singh (*loc. cit.*) as a result of the study of optical rotations of these two compounds have come to the conclusion that they show geometrical isomerism. Bhatnagar, Mathur and Neogi (*Z. Physik*, 1930, 69, 373) have, however, shown that although geometrical isomerides show difference in the values of magnetic susceptibility, the difference is not very marked, being, in their case, of the order 0.032×10^7 to 0.052×10^7 only.

The compounds under discussion are diamagnetic to start with and become paramagnetic on exposure to the action of light. This, however, does not support the view that the compound becomes converted into its isomeride and the paramagnetism may be indicative of either polymerisation or the production of free radicals. In the case of styrene, however, Bhatnagar, Kapur and Kaur (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 173) have shown that the large change observed in the susceptibility value of styrene on polymerisation cannot be explained only on the constitutional changes involved during the process of polymerisation. They have suggested that under the influence of magnetic field, an isotropic molecule of polystyrene orientates along the lines of force and gives the high susceptibility value observed. A similar view could be advanced in the case of these compounds, but the restoration of the original value on keeping the substances in the dark does not lend support to this. It is, therefore, probable that the substances produce free radicals when exposed to the action of sunlight.

In the free radicals, molecules are supposed to contain an odd number of electrons, which, as is commonly known, results in the paramagnetism of the molecule due to the existence of resultant spin moment. Theoretically the maximum magnetic moment of the substance on exposure to light should approach the value of $2 \times 1.73 = 3.46$ Bohr magneton (since the spin moment of an unbalanced electron in each radical should contribute a value of 1.73 Bohr magnetons). This will hold good only if the conversion is practically complete on exposure to light. It is obvious that the decomposition is only slight and the experimental values of magnetic susceptibilities become constant after a short time (*vide* Table I).

The molecular weight determination of the substance in benzene solution by freezing point method shows no sign of difference before and after exposure to sunlight. This method, as expected, is not of much help to indicate the formation of free radicals as tentatively represented by the equation given above.

The work which presented unusual difficulties as regards the preparation of these compounds is being continued.

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